

The Role of Female Christian Educators in Fostering Gender Equality For Sustainable Development In Nigeria

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Abstract

Female Christian Educators play a pivotal role in sustainable development by bridging the gap between moral/ethical formation and social responsibility, serving as agents of transformation within their communities. They contribute to sustainable development by fostering quality education, promoting gender equality, nurturing environmental stewardship, and advocating for social justice and peace building. The aim of this paper is to analyse the role of Christian Educators in fostering gender equality for sustainable development in Nigeria and to examine various contributions of female Christian Educators. This paper adopts a multidisciplinary approach to explore the interconnection between Sustainable Development Goals 4 and 5 (Quality Education and Gender Equality Respectively) in Nigeria, focusing on how Gender Equality influence development outcomes. The finding was that women in contemporary times are not given equal rights like their male counterpart in political, social, religious, and some other spheres of life. On this note, the role of Female Christian Educators in ensuring Sustainable Development Goal 5 cannot be overemphasized as they serve as catalyst for change in both religious and secular spheres using their influence to advocate for improved living conditions and social reforms. The paper concluded that, through their holistic approach, female Christian Educators merge spiritual, social and economic empowerment, driving sustainable development at the individual, community, and national levels. Consequently, the study recommends, amongst others, that women should be given equal rights with their male counterpart in every sphere of life particularly in Nigeria and in other parts of the world so as to foster sustainable development.

Keywords: Female Christian Educators, Gender Equality, Sustainable, Development

Introduction

Female Christian Educators play a pivotal role in sustainable development by bridging the gap between moral/ethical formation and social responsibility, serving as agent of transformation within their communities. Gender discrimination is as old as human history and cuts across different societies, cultures and religions. From the time of creation to the present day, there has been no time when both males and females were considered equal or seen to be so by the society. People (both men and women) have come to live with it as they see it as norm. Also, some societies have accepted it as *fait accompli* and that any struggle for equality between men and women is not possible (Egboh, Obioji and Agbata, 2010). Whereas sustainable development cannot be achieved without gender equality. Gender Equality is the process of allocating resources, programmes, and decisions fairly to both males and females without any form of discrimination and addressing the imbalances in the benefits available to males and females (Pathania, 2017).

According to Nwajiuba (2011), gender role differences worldwide seem to be a natural phenomenon, which has brought about gaps in enjoying specific opportunities by men and women pointing out these developments has recently become worrisome to some clamouring, the female folk are given unhindered access to contribute to the development and be involved in policy-making. As a result, international programs and conferences now focus on women intending to incorporate women into the development agenda based on equality with their male counterparts. In the last four decades, an international conference on women was organized by the United Nations in Mexico in 1975, Copenhagen in 1980, and China, Beijing in 1991. In Nigeria, these forums' agenda comprise achieving gender equality in national development among several issues. Several facts that hostile gender relations, such as unequal access to power and resources, gender-based division of labour, gender biases in rights and privileges remain on the increase (Aina, 2012). National Gender Policies 2007 ascertain that policy on gender like the "affirmative action in Nigeria structured in most cases with the ideas of Goal 4 (Gender Equality) and 'women empowerment,' and to also lend voices to women's support and increased opportunities for women's health, education, employment, and to improve their required socio-economic conditions. Nevertheless, as was earlier noted, many of such programs have failed and have deepened the crises at other times.

Consequently, failure to acknowledge women's role will make human society's development efforts practically impossible due to the unique functions embedded in each gender. Therefore, an essential tool for society's development is understanding gender role from Goal 4 perspectives which is imperative for sustainable developments in Nigeria. Some scholars like Olufemi and VerEecke (1992) have noted that according to equal worth and significance to gender roles performed by men and women will restore the stability and unity that were in existence in the African traditional societies. Thus, it is an important fact and implication of a development strategy to ensure that both women and men understand gender and gender roles.

Literature Review

The intersection of Gender Equality and Sustainable Development has been widely examined, emphasizing theoretical perspectives, policy frameworks, and practical challenges. This section synthesizes key insights from scholarly research, policy documents, and international agreements to contextualize the study.

Theoretical Foundations: Gender Equality is integral to sustainable development as highlighted in feminist theory and development study. Sen's capability approach emphasizes that individuals can differ greatly in their abilities to convert the same resources into valuable functioning ('beings' and 'doings'). For example, those with physical disabilities may need specific goods to achieve mobility and pregnant women have specific nutritional requirements to achieve good health. Therefore, evaluation that focuses only on a means, without considering what particular people can do with them is insufficient. Furthermore, Sen's approach ascertain that reality is complicated and that evaluation should reflect such complexity rather than take a short-cut by excluding all sorts of information from consideration in advance. For example, although it may seem obvious that happiness matters for the evaluation of how well people are doing, it is not all obvious that it should be the only aspect that ever matters, and so, nothing else should be considered. Therefore, evaluation of how well people are doing must seek to be as open-minded as possible.

According to Nussbaum capacity theory of justice, human being should be able to live to the end of human life of normal length, not dying prematurely, or before one's life is so reduced as to be not worth living. Furthermore, having the social base of self-respect and non-humiliation, being able to

be treated as a dignified being whose worth is equal to that of others. This entails provisions of non-discrimination on the basis of race, sex, sexual orientation, ethnicity, cast, religion, and national origin (Nussbaum, 2000).

Policy and Framework Analysis: Global frameworks have played a significant role in positioning gender equality as a fundamental aspect of sustainable development.

The Rio Declaration (1992): The declaration recognized the critical role of women in environmental management and sustainable decision making (UN, 1992).

The Beijing Platform for Action (1995): The platform highlighted key concerns such as economic participation, political representation, and education access, linking them to sustainability (UN Women, 1995).

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Particularly, the SDGs emphasize gender equality as both a standalone goal and a cross-cutting issue affecting all its goals (UN, 2015).

Case Study: Practical example showcase both advancement and areas requiring improvement. Initiatives such as the Gender Equality Seal Certification Program by UNDP have institutionalize gender sensitive practices in organizations, demonstrating measureable progress (UNDP, 2021). However, gaps persists, as seen in climate adaptation policies where gender considerations remain insufficiently integrated, particularly in post-disaster recovery efforts (UN Women, 2020).

Emerging Trends: Recent studies explore the link between gender equality and pressing global challenges, including technology access and public health. The adoption of gender-specific metrics, such as the Gender Development Index (GDI), represent a growing effort to track progress more effectively (UNDP, 2021).

This literature review provides a foundation for understanding how gender equality contributes to sustainable development, guiding further analysis and policy recommendations.

Evolution of the Concept: In recent years, there has been increasing recognition of the essential roles that gender equality, women's empowerment, and the protection of women's right play in fostering sustainable development. This recognition is reflected in multiple international agreements

and policy frameworks. For instance, Principle 20 of the 1992 Rio Declaration of environment and development highlights the necessity of women active participation in achieving sustainability goals (UN, 1992). Likewise, the 1995 Beijing Declaration and platform for action urge government to integrate gender perspectives into policies and programs related to sustainable developments (UN Women, 1995). The importance of gender equality was reaffirmed in the 2012 United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development outcome document. An article titled, “The Future We Want” emphasized the need for women empowerment across economic, social and environmental spheres. It also called for greater efforts to ensure women’s full participation in policy making, program implementation, and decision making at all levels (UN, 2012). The relationship between gender equality and sustainable development is crucial for several reasons: First, it is a fundamental ethical and moral obligation ensuring women’s right, dignity and opportunities is essential for building a just and equitable society.

Second, addressing gender disparities is necessary to mitigate the disproportionate economic, social, and environmental challenges that women and girls face, particularly in their roles within families and communities which are often undervalued (Sen, 1999). Lastly, empowering women by increasing their leadership contribute to a stronger connection between gender equality and sustainable development, leading to more inclusive and effective outcomes. Treating people unfairly because of their gender creates unjust societies teeming with inequality. Women, girls, transgender people and gender-diverse people face more discrimination which affects their access to good education, jobs, healthcare, legal protection, and much more.

Conceptual Framework

Gender inequality

Gender as a concept as has been a global phenomenon for a long time. Sex is defined as the biological categorization of male or female, as determined by physical variations in genetic compositions, reproductive architecture, and function. Gender refers to the social, cultural, and physical meanings, behaviours, activities, and characteristics that a society considers as proper for male and female members. This social classification of male and female is based on a collection of psychological characteristics and role aspects that society has allocated to the biological category of

sex. This is what Akpabio (2015) means when he defines gender as the socially, culturally, and manufactured roles that men and women play in society; roles that are formed by economic, historical, religious and cultural factors. In any particular social environment or context, such structures are built for the purpose of allocating powers, duties, responsibilities, statuses, and positions. Gender inequality refers to persons being treated differently and unfairly based on their gender, resulting in unequal access to opportunities and resources.

Discussion of Issues

Some issues found in this study are that, achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls is not just the right thing to do, it is essential for sustainable development. *Goal 5* focuses on closing the gender gap and ensuring equal opportunities for all. Gender Equality is not only a fundamental human right, but a necessary foundation for a peaceful, prosperous and sustainable world. There has been progress over the last decades, but the world is not on track to achieve gender equality by 2030. Also, it was discovered that women and girls represent half of the world's population, and therefore, also half of its potential, but gender inequality persist everywhere and stagnates social progress. Sexual violence and exploitation, the unequal division of unpaid care and discrimination in public offices all remain huge barriers. Findings indicate that while progress has been made in education and health, significant global gender gaps persist in political empowerment, economic participation and leadership position.

More so, persistent barriers which has to do with cultural biases, negative stereotype, patriarchal structures continue to hinder progress. Lastly, integrating SDGs 4 & 5 are essential for sustainable development as education empowers women to assert rights while gender equality enables equal access to learning. This synergy boosts economic growth, reduces poverty and improve health outcomes as education for women and girls often ripples outward to improve quality of life.

According to a report published by United Nation Women in September 2022, it could take close to 300 years to achieve full gender equality at the current rate of progress. The global pandemic, conflict, the climate crisis and a harsh backlash against women's sexual and reproductive health and rights are further diminishing the outlook for gender equality. Below are some facts about the state of global gender inequality today.

- i. Not a single country in the world has achieved gender equality: On a global level, there has been little progress on gender equality since the Global Goals were signed in 2015. A third of countries have made no progress since then, and of these, 18 countries have seen gender inequality worsen, with Venezuela, Afghanistan, Algeria, Belarus, Kuwait, and Ecuador the worst affected. The worst countries for gender inequality for 2022 were Sudan, Yemen, Afghanistan and Chad. South Sudan, has some of the highest rate for forced marriage and maternal mortality. In Chad, child marriage is also wide spread among girls, reducing girls' education and resulting in one of the highest rate of early child bearing worldwide.
- ii. Over 380 million women and girls are living in extreme poverty: Poverty is not gender neutral. In fact, majority of the world's poor are women. Why? Poverty disproportionately affect women because they do not have as many opportunities as men to receive an education, work or own property.
- iii. There are more forcibly displaced women and girls than ever before: For women, displacement is not the end of their problems, it is only the beginning. They often lose their properties, assets, livelihoods and access to health care. It also exposes them to greater risks of violence, trafficking and sexual abuse.
- iv. Women hold just 26.5% of parliamentary seats: As of January 2023, women held just over a quarter of parliamentary seats around the world. Only 13 countries, mostly in Europe have gender-equal cabinet. This is not about to change any time soon with the earliest date for parity forecast for 2062.
- v. Women earn just 77 cents for every dollar men earn: Although the global gender gap narrowed slightly between 2022 and 2023, women still earned less money over the span of their working lives than men. Factors that contribute to these gender-based wealth inequality are gender pay gaps, unequal career progression, trajectories, and gender gaps in financial literacy and life events.
- vi. Another fact about gender inequality around the world which is typically against Goal 5 (Gender Equality) is the current decision of the International Olympic Committees which banned transgender women and DSD (Differences in Sex Development) athletes from the female category of events at the 2028 Los Angeles Olympic and Future Games. Kirsty

Coventry, the president of the IOC (International Olympic Committees) said the land mark decision has been taken because “it would not be fair for biological males to compete in the female category. The IOC has also confirmed that all athletes wanting to compete in the female category at future Olympics will have to undergo a one-off SRY (Sex determining Region Y gene) screening to detect their biological sex. Usually, that is done via an unintrusive cheek-swap or saliva test.

The IOC stated that its new policy should be adopted by all international sports federations and governing bodies for events, such as the summer and winter Olympics. It was made clear that it applies only to elite sport and not any grassroots or recreational sport programs. However, this decision of IOC is apparently against the *Goal 5*. Many girls and women with this condition, also called DSD do not even know it, the IOC is unbothered by this landmine, lobbing off when the suggestion that someone else should consider offering mental health resources to women who test positive. Imagine the psychological devastation of discovering you cannot compete, and then learning it is because you have a condition that, in the eye of the IOC make you not a “real woman.” However, fairness in competition is important but eligibility rules must also be proportionate and aligned with contemporary standards of DSD care, rather than creating foreseeable and avoidable harm to these vulnerable minority group.

Causes of Gender Inequality

The following are some causes of gender inequality

Unequal Education

When everyone gets good education, there are better job opportunities, higher incomes, less violence and better health. Historically, more girls seems to have been excluded from education than boys. While the global gender gap in education is shrinking, Sub-Saharan Africa has not achieved gender parity at any level of education. According to GEM’s 2024 Gender Report; Afghanistan bans secondary and higher education for women, about 1.4million Afghan girls are reportedly excluded from education. Inequality in education affects not only girls but entire societies by increasing the risk of poverty, child mortality and conflict.

Employment Segregation

Employment segregation is the unequal distribution of men and women in the workforce. A report from the World Bank's group describes horizontal and vertical segregation which means men and women can be concentrated across different industries and occupations, as well as unequally distributed in promotions and manager roles. Globally, women tend to work in vulnerable, low-paying jobs like care works, while men have more access to higher-paying and stable careers. Gender Inequality would not end with employing more women in those jobs that do not pay well or that have opportunities for growth. For instance, from September 2022 – 2024, women in India comprised 41% of new comers to the workforce but women were over represented in low-wage industries.

Restrictive Laws

Some countries institutionalize gender inequality. According to a 2022 World Bank report 178 countries have legal barriers that restrict the economic participation of about 2.4 billion women. Ninety-five countries do not ensure equal pay for equal work between men and women. Other discriminatory laws include Saudi Arabia's personal status law, which desires women equal rights during a divorce, and Afghanistan's "Vice and Virtue" laws which ban women from speaking or showing their faces outside the home. Laws that discriminate based on gender disempower women and cause significant inequality.

Gender-Based Violence

Gender-based violence is any violence directed at a person due to their gender. Most victims of intimate partner and family related murder are women according to data from the United Nations Office, on Drugs and Crimes. Every day, more than 133 women or girls are killed by someone in their family. By age 19, one in four women who have been in relationship have already experienced physical, sexual or psychological abuse by a partner. A world that is unsafe for women is inherently unequal.

Threats to Reproductive Rights

Reproductive rights serve as bed rock of gender equality. Without the freedom to choose if and when to have children, women experience threats to their health, education, careers, and safety. Researchers have also noticed a link between domestic violence and abortion restrictions. When women cannot

access abortion, rate of intimate partners' violence increase, threats to reproductive rights deepen existing gender inequality.

Religious Intolerance

In the human rights field, religious freedom and human rights can clash but as researcher Marie Juul, Petersen writes, research demonstrates a “Strong Correlation” between countries that restrict religions and perpetuate gender inequality. Consider how extremist religious groups like the Taliban in Afghanistan attack women, girls, and religious minorities. Religious intolerance also includes banning peaceful displays of religious belief, like how France banned headscarves for French female athletes competing in the 2024 Olympics. To protect women and gender equality, religious tolerance is a value to be encouraged, not disallowed.

Transphobia

Transphobia, which is a prejudice or hatred toward transgender people, is a form of gender discrimination. Gender inequality discussions tend to focus on women and girls, but transgender and gender-diverse people face stark inequalities too. According to the United Nations, most of the world's Trans people lack legal protection, lack recognition by the State, and face higher rates of violence and stigma. At least 9 countries have laws targeting trans and gender-diverse people with punishments like fines, forced counselling, and imprisonment. Solution to gender inequality must include protection for all oppressed gender.

Roles of Women in Development of the Society

The rate at which women's contributions to the development of the society is being downplayed has become exasperatingly worrisome in recent times. History has it that women have contributed tremendously to the development of many societies, including Nigeria, because of their endowment with capabilities and qualities meant to complement those of the men folks in the society. In line with the above, Onwunyi (2018) noted that over time in history, few women who have been entrusted with the leading role to manage human and material resources have more often than not proved the same that, given adequate backing and free hand, they can exceed normal expectations. A look at some of the areas where women have excelled and keep excelling in their efforts towards societal development will lend more credence to the assertion above.

For instance, in the community development and youth empowerment, women have done relatively enough as they do not fail to register their influence in every community development project through their huge financial donations. They also build skill acquisition centres, where unemployed youths and indigent rural women can acquire skills such as bread-baking skills, fashion and designing, soap-making, pomade-making, computer repairs and programming, hair dressing, GSM repairs, interior decorations, bead-making, et cetera that help to provide jobs for jobless youths in their various communities. Unemployment and poverty are pervasive among the rural dwellers because the people are backward and underdeveloped and cannot afford minimum standard of living (Iheanacho 2016). Women's continuous advancement in contributing to societal peace and stability has impacted on the peace, unity, progress and socio-economic wellbeing of the society. Awe (1990) in Onwunyi (2018) sees the importance of women from their roles as promoters of peace and stability at homes and communities through their inherent managerial abilities.

Another area where women have played outstanding role in the development of the society is in family advancement. Women are naturally industrious, creative and financially intelligent. They have succeeded in transforming the bleak economies of their families, communities, local governments, states, and nations to vibrant economies through their inherent economic strength, managerial skill, innovative ideas and their capacities to partner with visionary men (Akosile 2010 in Njoku 2018). Similarly, women contribute to the development of the society through children moral development. Women take the duty of children good up-bringing and sound moral development as part of their primary responsibility. They show high concern in producing children who when they grow into full adults will contribute meaningfully to natural development, using their fully developed potentials (Awusaku & Ugwulebo 2013).

Women are found at various acting points in value chain and agricultural sector either as primary producers, processors, input suppliers, commercial buying agents and marketing linkage providers (Urom, Ibiam, Abu & Chukwuoko 2020). Without women, agricultural activities in general would have been put into extinction in most of our rural communities. More so, in politics, women have contributed significantly, shaping our national democracy and entire political system through the creation of political awareness among women and politicians. Women have arisen to demand for

more representation in keeping with the principle of representative democracy which holds among others, that elected assemblies should reflect composition of the electorate (Njoku 2018). Women constitute greater percentage of the electorate in Nigeria and other African countries today. The days are gone when women bow low to political intimidation and marginalization by the menfolk. They have influenced the government to realize that democracy presupposes a genuine partnership between men and women in the conduct of the affairs of the society in which they work in equality and complementary drawing mutual women and known for their capability to bring about a paradigm shift in the political landscape of the society. Alapiki (2004) in Njoku (2018) remarks that “experience from across the world where women play key roles in public office has shown that women politics and decision making contribute to redefining political priorities, placing new items on the political agenda that reflect and address concerns as well as providing new perspectives on mainstream political issues.

Conclusion

Gender Equality is both moral and strategic necessity for advancing sustainable development and tackling global challenges. The need to recognize the right and dignity of women in the society is becoming very important. In the social and religious affairs, the exclusion of women in male dominated systems has been a long standing issue. Women play very significant roles in society development in spite of hindrances. It is high time such impediments that have allowed men to occupy and enjoy all the positions of honour in the society be removed so that women would come up and take leadership positions in the society. If we should go back to the drawing board, one would unequivocally agree that the society cannot stand strong without the contribution of women. To create a just and sustainable world, efforts must focus on dismantling structural inequalities, empowering women through education and economic opportunities, and ensuring inclusivity across development areas. This includes addressing the specific challenges faced by marginalized groups, ensuring equal access to resources and reshaping societal norms that upholds gender disparities (Nussbaum, 2000: UN. Women, 2021). Consequently, the study has examined the causes of gender inequality and discussed the role of women in society development. It also highlighted some roles of Christian

Educators in fostering gender equality for sustainable development while providing some recommendations in the following.

Recommendations

In order to enhance women capacity to play more efficient roles in the nation development, this paper recommends the following:

1. The society should abolish cultural beliefs and traditional practices that make women have limited access to economic rights and privileges.
2. Religious institutions are expected to combat traditional interpretations of scriptures that upholds gender inequality. This includes redefining roles to promote gender equality and justice rather than discrimination.
3. Religious bodies should have zero tolerance for violence against women and girls, both within their communities and society at large.
4. Women should always recognize their worth and position in their quest for societal development and national transformation and so should braze up to confront gallantly, all the social, religious, economic, and political impediments that hold them down.
5. The government should take practical steps to emphasize and at the same time make special funds available for girl-children education in the society, especially those from the poor, to enable access quality education.
6. The government should synergize efforts to douse the flame of inequality kindled and fanned by the patriarchal structure of our environment by creating a platform of equality and inclusiveness that would enable men and women have equal access to decision making structures, organizations and institutions that affects their lives.
7. Members of the society should cooperate and give unflinching support to the women folks in their effort to contribute diversely to the development of the society. All the wrong notions, cultural bias, and stereotypical belief about women should be thrown overboard in order to fully harness the galaxy of their natural endowment for national development.

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